

Ethnopharmacological Survey of Medicinal Plants Used against Malaria in Butembo City (D. R. Congo).

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ABSTRACT

Malaria is a major global public health problem in the world especially in the Democratic Republic of Congo. An Ethnopharmacological survey was conducted in Butembo city (Democratic Republic of Congo) in order to identify the plant species used in traditional medicine for the treatment of malaria. Fifty-four healers belonging to different ethnic groups were interviewed about the plant species used in traditional medicine for the management of malaria in the city of Butembo. The name of the plants, the plant parts, the modes of preparation and the modes of administration of recipes were recorded. Cited plants were collected and identified at herbarium of the Laboratory of Ecology and Plants Resource Management, Faculty of Sciences, "Université Officielle de Bukavu". The plants ecological status was also determined. Forty six species of plants belonging to twenty seven botanical families were identified. The main habitat preference of species is cultivated (56%), trees constituted 37% of morphological type while 42% of biological type are Microphanerophytes and Nanophanerophytes (each one 21%). The decoction was the main mode of preparation (80 %). Leaves constituted 67 % of plant organs used for drug preparation. Some plant species cited (54%) are known in the literature to possess antimalarial activity. Further studies should be undertaken to investigate effectiveness of other plants that have not yet been studied and to determine their chemical composition.

Keywords: Medicinal plants, malaria, decoction, Butembo, Democratic Republic of the Congo.

INTRODUCTION

Malaria is a major global public health problem, and the alarming spread of drug resistance and limited number of effective drugs now available underline how important it is to discover new antimalarial compounds. It is caused by parasites of the genus *Plasmodium* and is one of the leading infectious diseases in many tropical regions [1,2].

Nearly half of the world's population is exposed to malaria. According to WHO world malaria report 2013, there were an estimated 207 million cases of malaria worldwide in 2012. Most of the estimated cases (80%) occur in sub-Saharan Africa. About 9% of estimated cases globally are due to *P. vivax*, although the proportion outside the African continent is 50% [3].

There were an estimated 627 000 malaria deaths worldwide in 2012. Of the estimated deaths, most occur in sub-Saharan Africa (90%) and in children under 5 years of age (77%) [4]. Malaria is a major public health threat in Africa, and traditional medicine continues to play a key role in its control, especially in rural areas [5].

The success of the antimalarial drug quinine and the discovery of artemisinin, the most potent antimalarial drug, both from plant sources, has led to the study of plants as antimalarial agents. The ethnopharmacological approach for the search of new antimalarial agents from plant sources has proved to be more predictive. To overcome the problem of increasing drug resistance, traditional medicines are an important source for potential new anti-malarials [6-8].

The Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC) is by far the African country with the highest biodiversity [9]. The flora of the DRC is among the richest in the world. At least 50,000 plant species of which 10% are oil-bearing potential [10]. It is therefore imperative that Congolese biodiversity should be screened in order to find compounds from plants used in traditional medicine that can give new antimalarial drugs. In the present work, we report on the plants, which have been identified as antimalarial plants in Congolese traditional medicine in the Butembo City, located in the east part of the DRC.

EXPERIMENTAL

Study Area

The Ethnopharmacological investigations were conducted in Butembo, one of the cities of the North Kivu province, located in the eastern part of DRC (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1: Location of Butembo City [11]

Butembo is a city in North Kivu, in the north eastern Democratic Republic of Congo, lying west of the Virunga National Park. Until the Congo Civil War, it was an important commercial center with a large market, a cathedral, a small hospital, and an airport, lying in an area known for tea and coffee growing. As of 2010 it had an estimated population of 200,000.

Administratively, the city has four “communes”: Bulengera, Kimemi, Mususa and Vulamba. The terminal indicating the line of the equator is about 20 kilometers south of the city. The town is situated at 1800 m of altitude and at 280 km from Goma, the greatest city of the east of DRC. The surrounding villages are home to plantations of tea, coffee and cinchona [12].

Ethnopharmacological Survey

Ethnopharmacological surveys were conducted for 8 months, from November 2010 to June 2011. Fifty-four traditional healers were identified and interviewed on a voluntary basis. The data checklist for Ethnobotanical field work focuses on the following elements [13]:

- ❖ Identification of the traditional healer (name, age, address, quality)
- ❖ Plant data (scientific and vernacular names, village survey, parts used, and method of harvesting stage or degree and organ development)

- ❖ Plant therapy data: methods of preparation and administration (transaction and pharmaceutical form, concentration of the organ dose, frequency of taking, instructions and any other associated plants)
- ❖ Other indications (diseases and symptoms, physiological effects, against indications and side effects).
- ❖ Collected plants were identified at the Laboratory of Ecology and Plant Resources Management, Faculty of Science and applied sciences of “Université Officielle de Bukavu”, D.R Congo. Vouchers specimens are on deposit at the same laboratory.

Floristic Characterizations of Plants Collected

Medicinal plants used in traditional medicine against malaria in Butembo are characterized in this work by their morphological types, biological types, habitat types and Phytogeographical distribution.

a. The morphological types have been inventoried as following: tree (T), shrub (Sh), Sub-shrub (Ssh), annual herb (Ah), vivace herb (Vh), perennial herb (Ph), and liana (L).

b. Biological types below have been selected: Mesophanerophytes (MsPh), Microphanerophytes (McPh), Nanophanerophytes (NPh), Chamaephytes (Ch), Therophytes (Th), Theophytes scapeux (Tsc), Chamephytes (Ch), erected Chamephytes (Ch er), climbing chamephytes (Ch cl) and Geophytes (G).

c. Habitat types are distributed as following: cultured (Cult), sub-spontaneous cultured (Cult ssp), forest (Fo), Fallow (Fal) and ruderal (Rud).

d. The phytogeographical types of distribution presented in this work are defined in accordance with the chorological subdivisions agreed for the Central African region [14-19].

These are:

Cosmopolitan (Cosm.), Pantropical (Pan), Paleotropical (Pal), Afro-tropical (Af tr), Guinean (Guin), Centroguinean (C-Guin), American tropical (Am tr), tropical Asia (Asia tr), American and Australia [18].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Forty six species of plants used in Butembo city (DRC) for the management of malaria were identified. These plants are arranged in alphabetical order of family's and species and listed in Tables 1 and 2.

Table.1: Ecological characteristics of plants used against malaria in Butembo city (DRC)

Families	Plants species	Used part	Treated diseases (Symptoms)	Vernacular name (Language)	Preparation mode (Solvent)	Frequency (%)
Alliaceae	<i>Allium sativum</i> L.	Bulbs	Wound disinfectant	Ehayi (K)	Pounding	9a 0b
			Intestinal infections			
Apocynaceae	<i>Catharanthus roseus</i>	Leaves	Diabetes.	Vinga (K)	Decoction (water)	11a 2,5b

ceae	(L.) G. Don					
		Roots	Urogenital infections			
	<i>Rawolfia vomitoria</i> Afzel	Bark	Intestinal worms	Akatongo kube (K)	Decoction (water)	28a 17,5b
			Hypertension			
Aristolochiaceae	<i>Aristolochia sp.</i>	Seed	-	Amarinda (K)	Maceration (water)	12a 2,5b
				Ekyambe (K)		
Asteraceae	<i>Achillea millefolium</i> L.	Leaves	-	-	Decoction (water)	5,5a 0b
	<i>Ageratum conyzoides</i> (L.) L.	Leaves	Poisoning	Olupapali (K)	Decoction (water)	31,5a 10b
	<i>Artemisia annua</i> L.	Leaves	-	-	Infusion (water)	74a NDb
	<i>Bidens pilosa</i> L.	Leaves	Typhoid fever	Obukuto (K)	Decoction (water)	39a 10b
	<i>Conyza sumentrensis</i> (Retz.) E.Walker	Leaves	Abdominal pain	Akabingande (K)	Decoction (water)	24b 5b
	<i>Crassocephalum monthuosum</i> (S.Moore) Milme-Redh	Leaves	Typhoid fever	Ekisulanindi (K)	Decoction (water)	9b 0b
	<i>Matricaria chamomilla</i> L.	Leaves	Dysmenorrhoeal	-	Decoction (water)	65a 2,5b
			Immune depression			
	<i>Microglossa pyrifolia</i> (Lam.) Kuntze	Leaves	Ovarian Cyst	Embatule (K)	Decoction (water)	18,5a 5b
				Kabeba mimba (S)		
	<i>Mikania cordata</i> (Burm.f.) B.L.Rob	Leaves	Abdominal pain	Engulapo	Decoction (water)	57,5a 17,5b
	<i>Sambucus mexicana</i> C.Presl ex DC.	Leaves	Typhoid fever	-	Decoction (water)	13a 0b
			Urogenital infections			
	<i>Tithonia diversifolia</i> (Hemsl.) A. Cray.	Leaves	Fibroma	Ekiwa (K)	Decoction (water)	55,5a 10b
			Blennorrhoea			
			Ovarian Cyst			
			Typhoid fever			
	<i>Vernonia amygdalina</i> Del.	Leaves	Diabetes.	Omubĩrĩrĩ (K)	Decoction (water)	62a 22,5b
			Immune depression			
			Abdominal pain			
			Liver complications			
	<i>Zebrina pendula</i> Schnizl	Leaves	Typhoid fever	Endetsa ye rangi	Decoction (water)	20a 0b
		Fruit	yomusasi			
Boraginaceae	<i>Cynoglossum loncesletum</i> Fors.	Leaves	Hypertension	Ekituvā (K)	Decoction (water)	9b 0b
			Gastritis	Sukuma wuki (S)		
Bromeliac	<i>Ananas cosmesus</i> (L.)	Fruit wall	Typhoid fever	Erinanasu (K)	Expression	10a 0b

ae	Merr.						
Caricaceae	<i>Carica papaya</i> L.	Leaves	Intestinal worms	Epayĩpapĩ	Decoction (water)	41a 12,5b	
Chenopodiaceae	<i>Chenopodium ambrosioides</i> L.	Leaves	Abdominal pain	Omunduluma (K)	Decoction (water)	68,5a 37,5b	
Cupressaceae	<i>Cupressus lusitanica</i> Mill.	Leaves	Hemorrhoids	Ekilau (K)	Decoction (water)	39a 0b	
Euphorbiaceae	<i>Croton sp.</i>	Bark	Intestinal worms	Omutsĩkĩĩ (K)	Decoction (water)	10a 0b	
			Headache				
			Pelvic pain				
			Tumour				
Fabaceae	<i>Arachis hypogaea</i> L.	Seed	Typhoid fever.	AKalanga(K), Kalanga (S)	Paste	12a 0b	
	<i>Cassia occidentalis</i> L.	Leaves	Epilepsy	Omwita nzoka (K)	Decoction (water)	54 17,5b	
	<i>Erythrina abyssinica</i>	Bark	Yellow fever	Omukohwa (K)	Decoction (water)	9b 0b	
Lamiaceae	<i>Leucas martilicensis</i> (Jacq.) R.Br	Leaves	-	Akanya makundo kake (K)	Decoction (water)	10a 0b	
		Stem					
	<i>Mentha piperita</i> L.	Leaves	Cold	Ehistsanyi	Decoction (water)	29,5a 0b	
			Cough				
			Intestinal worms				
	<i>Tetradernia ruparia</i> (Hochst). Codd.	Leaves	Mental disorder	Omutubya (K)	Expression	26 0b	
Lauraceae	<i>Persea americana</i> Mill.	Fruit	Intestinal worms	Efuka (K)	Decoction (water)	39a 0b	
Meliaceae	<i>Azadirachta indica</i> A. Juss	Leaves	Typhoid fever	Arubaini (S)	Decoction (water)	42,5a 42,5b	
					Dira (K)		
Myrtaceae	<i>Callistemon speciosus</i> (Sims) D.C	Leaves	-	-	Decoction (water)	10a 0b	
	<i>Eucalyptus sp.</i>	Stem	-	-	Infusion (water)	51a 7,5b	
	<i>Eucalyptus globulus</i> L.	Leaves	Typhoid fever.	Omutusu we mbamba	Decoction (water)	55,5a 10b	
	<i>Psidium guayava</i> L.	Leaves	Diarrhea	Amapera (K)	Decoction (water)	48a 12,5b	
	<i>Syzygium guineense</i> (Willd) DC.	Bark	Headache	Omutusu (K)	Decoction (water)	12a 2,5b	
				Intestinal worms			
Ranunculaceae	<i>Ranunculus multifidus</i> Forssk	Leaves	Abdominal pain	Kivunja homa (S)	Decoction (water)	10a 0b	
					Enyarubanda (K)		
Passifloraceae	<i>Passiflora edulis</i> Sims.	Leaves	Typhoid fever	Amarikucha (K)	Decoction (water)	5,5a 0b	
					Blennorrhoea		
					Ovarian Cyst		
Poaceae	<i>Cymbopogon citratus</i> (DC) Stapf.	Leaves	Asthma	Ebitsayi (K)	Decoction (water)	44,5a 27,5b	
					Bronchitis		

			Cough			
			Cold			
Rosaceae	<i>Rubus inedulis</i> L.	Leaves	-	Amakerere (K)	Decoction (water)	10a 0b
Rubiaceae	<i>Cinchona ledgeriana</i> Moes.	Bark	-	Kenkina (S)	Decoction (water)	83,5a NDb
Rutaceae	<i>Citrus limon</i> (L.) Burn.f	Leaves	Fever	Chunghwa kali (S)	Decoction (water)	50a 12,5b
			Flu			
			Abdominal pain			
Solanaceae	<i>Physalis peruviana</i> L.	Leaves	-	Embupuru (K)	Decoction (water)	9a 0b
Trepelocaea	<i>Tropaeolum majus</i> L.	Leaves	Cough	-	Decoction (water)	12,5a 0b
			Typhoid fever			
			Urinary infections			
Verbenaceae	<i>Lantana camara</i> L.	Leaves	Cough	Amakulumbe (K)	Decoction (water)	37,5a 15b
Xanthorrhoeaceae	<i>Aloe dawei</i> A. Berger	Leaves	-	Engaka (K)	Decoction (water)	46a 5b

a. Frequency of citation by traditional healers (number of times out of 54 interviewees)

b. Frequency of citation in the literature (number of articles retrieved during the search period mentioning the plant as antimalarial)

ND: No determined

K : Kinande S : Swahili

Table.2: Plants used against malaria in Butembo city (DRC)

Families	Plants species	Morphological type	Biological type	Habitat type	Phyto-geographical Distribution
Alliaceae	<i>Allium sativum</i> L.	Vh	G	Cult.	Cosm.
Apocyanaceae	<i>Catharanthus roseus</i> (L.)	Ssh	NPh	Cult.	Pan (Am tr)
	<i>Rawolfia vomitoria</i> Afzel	Sh	MsPh	Rud	Guin
Aristolochiaceae	<i>Aristolochia sp.</i>	Vh	Ph cl	Cult	Pan (Am tr)
Asteraceae	<i>Achillea millefolium</i> L.	Ah	McPh	Fo	Pan
	<i>Ageratum conyzoides</i> (L.)L.	Ah	Tsc	Rud	Pan
	<i>Artemisia annual</i> L.	Ah	NPh	Cult	Pal
	<i>Bidens pilosa</i> L.	Ah	Th	Rud	Pan
	<i>Conyza sumentrensis</i> (Retz.) E.Walker	Ah	Tsc	Rud	Pan
	<i>Crassocephalum monthuosum</i> (S.Moore) Milme-Redh	Ah	Tsc	Rud	Cosm
	<i>Matricaria chamomilla</i> L.	Ah	NPh	Fal	Cosm
	<i>Microglossa pyrifolia</i> (Lam.) Kuntze	T	NPh	Semi-aqu	Af tr
	<i>Mikania cordota</i> (Burm.f.) B.L.Rob	L	Ph cl	Fo	Pal

	<i>Sambucus mexicana</i> C.Presl ex DC.	T	NPh	Cult	Pan (Am tr)
	<i>Tithonia diversifolia</i> (Hemsl). A. Cray.	Ssh	NPh	Rud	Pan (Am tr)
	<i>Vernonia amygdalina</i> Del.	Sh	McPh	Fal	Af tr
	<i>Zebrina pendula</i> Schnizl	Vh	Ch	Cult ssp	Pan (Am tr)
Boraginaceae	<i>Cynoglossum loncesletum</i> Fors.	Ah	Tsc	Fal	Af tr
Bromeliaceae	<i>Ananascosmesus</i> (L.) Merr.	Vh	Ch er.	Cult ssp	Pan (Am tr)
Caricaceae	<i>Carica papaya</i> L.	T	McPh	Cult	Pan (Am tr)
Chenopodiaceae	<i>Chenopodium ambrosioides</i> L.	Ah	Tsc	Cult ssp	Cosm (Am tr)
Cupressaceae	<i>Cupressus lusitanica</i> Mill.	T	MsPh	Cult	Pan (Am tr)
Euphorbiaceae	<i>Croton sp.</i>	T	MsPh	Cult	C-Guin
Fabaceae	<i>Arachis hypogaea</i> L.	Ah	Tsc	Cult	Pan (Am tr)
	<i>Cassia occidentalis</i> L.	Ssh	NPh	Cult	Pan
	<i>Erythrina abyssinica</i>	T	McPh	Cult	C-Guin
Lamiaceae	<i>Leucas martilicensis</i> (Jacq.) R.Br	Vh	Th	Fal	Pan
	<i>Mentha piperita</i> L.	Ah	Th	Cult	Cosm
	<i>Tetradernia ruparia</i> (Hochst). Codd.	T	NPh	Cult ssp	Af tr
Lauraceae	<i>Persea americana</i> Mill.	T	MsPh	Cult	Pan (Am tr)
Meliaceae	<i>Azadirachta indica</i> A. Juss	T	MsPh	Cult	Pan (Asia tr)
Myrtaceae	<i>Callistemon specious</i> (Sims) D.C	T	MsPh	Cult	Pan (Australia)
	<i>Eucalyptus sp.</i>	T	MsPh	Cult	Pan
	<i>Eucalyptus globulus</i> L.	T	McPh	Cult	Pan
	<i>Psidium guayava</i> L.	T	McPh	Cult	Pan (Am tr)
	<i>Syzygium guineense</i> (Willd) DC.	T	MsPh	Cult	Af tr
Ranunculaceae	<i>Ranunculus multifidus</i> Forssk	Ph	McPh	Fal	Af tr
Passifloraceae	<i>Passiflora edulis</i> Sims.	L	Ph cl	Cult	Pan (Am tr)
Poaceae	<i>Cymbopogon citratus</i> (DC) Stapf.	Vh	Tsc	Cult	Pan (Asia tr)
Rosaceae	<i>Rubus inedulis</i> L.	L	Ph cl	Cult	Af tr
Rubiaceae	<i>Cinchona ledgeriana</i> Moes.	T	McPh	Cult	Af tr
Rutaceae	<i>Citrus limon</i> (L.) Burn.f	T	McPh	Cult	Pan
Solanaceae	<i>Physalis peruviana</i> L.	Ah	Th	Rud	Pan
Trepeolaceae	<i>Tropaeolum majus</i> L.	Vh	Ch er	Cult	Cosm (Am)
Verbenaceae	<i>Lantana camara</i> L.	T	NPh	Cult ssp	Pan (Am tr)
Xanthorrhoeaceae	<i>Aloe dawei</i> A. Berger	Ah	G	Cult	Pan

Morphological types

The Ethnopharmacological survey of plants used against malaria in Butembo city shows that ligneous plants represent

about 48% of species (Trees=37%, Sub-shrubs=7% and Shrubs=4%) while herbaceous and liana represent 52% (fig. 2).

Fig. 2: Weighted morphological types.

Biological types

The analysis of the biological types of the inventoried flora used in folk medicine against malaria in Butembo city (Fig. 3) indicates the predominance of Nanophanerophytes and Microphanerophytes (21%) each followed by Mesophanerophytes (19%) and Theophytes scapeux (16%).

Fig. 3: Weighted biological types.

Habitat preferences

Only the most characteristic habitat of each plant species is indicated. The types of habitats retained in this document are therefore: farms or crops which are cultivated species (56.5%), Fallow (10.8%), or plants found in the village Ruderal (15.2%), Sub-spontaneous Cultured (10.8%), semi-aquatic (2.1%) and Forest (4.3%).

Fig. 4 : Weighted biotopes types.

Phytogeographical distribution

The analysis of the Phytogeographic distribution of the inventoried flora against malaria in Butembo city (Fig. 5) indicates the predominance of Pan (24%) followed respectively by Pan (Am tr) (13.28%), Cosm (9%), Af tr (8.18%), Pan (Asia tr) (5%), Pal (4%), C-Guin (2.4%), Guin, Pan (Australia), Cosm (Am), and Cosm (Am tr) represent only 1.2% for each.

Fig. 5: Phytogeographical distribution Botanical Families Involved in the Study

Fig. 6: Distribution of species according to their botanical families.

Forty-six species of plants belonging to 25 different families were collected. Asteraceae family is the most represented with thirteen plant species (28%) followed by Myrtaceae with five on 46 species. Fabaceae and Lamiaceae possess three plant species each, Apocynaceae have two species and the others families are represented by one plant species each (Fig. 6).

Characteristic of Recipes of Medicinal Plants

Recipes used are characterized by the relative importance of plant parts, mode of preparation and administration used.

Plant parts used

The leaves are the most used parts in the treatment of malaria with medicinal plants in Butembo (Fig. 7). It represents almost 67.39% of used plant parts cited by traditional healers in this survey. The use of leaves could be justified by the abundance of chemical groups they contain. In fact, leaves are known as main synthesis site of secondary metabolites in plants

and are the most commonly used plant parts by traditional medicine practitioners [13,18-21].

Fig. 7: Weighted used parts

Mode of preparation of recipes

Water is the most used solvent for the preparation of the recipes (91.3%) and decoction is the main mode of preparation of remedies, it represents 85% of preparation modes (Fig.8). This confirms the results already reported by several other authors [18-19, 22-24]. In fact, water is the cheapest and the most available solvent that can dissolve a high number of metabolites and high temperature permits a rapid extraction of active ingredients. However, some of these metabolites can be degraded by heat.

Fig. 8: Mode of preparation of recipes

Administration route and dose

Careful observation and discussions with traditional healers during surveys revealed that traditional healers had knowledge of dosage and frequency of Phytomedicine to be administered. Frequency is often determined after observing physical condition of the patient (i.e. patient height, weight or age and history of ailments). So according to Adjanohoun [25], imperfections observed in traditional medicine seem to be no more injurious to health than those likely to occur in other forms of medicine. The simple fact of not finding the same frequency in regimens of traditional medicine is not sufficient to conclude incorrectly to the non-existence of African medicine dosages.

In general, the concentration or the amount of the organ, the dose, the frequency or the period of taking the product depends to the prescriber. In most cases, the drug is prescribed in two or

three doses. Usually a beer glass is taken as the first step of the assay and all preparations were administered orally (100% of cases).

Similarities of Use

Some species found in Tables 1 and 2, used in Butembo and its surroundings against malaria are commonly used as raw materials for some synthetic molecules and Phytomedicines against this disease. This is the case of quinine from *Chinchona ledgeriana* Moes bark, artemisinin from *Artemisia annua* L. The number of survey listing these species as antimalarial is not exhaustive. So that this work does not mention the frequency of bibliographic citation in the Table 2.

Eucalyptus globulus Labill (Called fever tree) and *Eucalyptus ssp.* is used in case of fever induced by *Plasmodium*. In fact, it's known that fever remains the main sign of malaria diagnosis [26-27]. Several other studies report the use of these two species in the treatment of malaria [22,28-32].

Kilma®, a Congolese phytomedicine, is a combination of *Lantana camara* L. with *Gardenia ternifolia* and *Crossopterix febrifuga* [33]. Many studies mention the use of this specie in support of malaria [22,31,34-36]. *Vernonia amygdalina*, *Chenopodium ambrosioides*, *Erythrina abyssinica*, *Lantana trifolia* (near *L. camara*) but also as *Aloe sp.*, are also indicated as antimalarial plants in Rwandan traditional medicine [37].

Bidens pilosa, *Aloe sp.*, *Vernonia sp.*, *Cassia didymobotrya* (species related to *C. occidentalis*), *Conyza sumentrensis*, *Croton* (with two species), *Microglossa pyrifolia* and *Rauwolfia mombasiana* (near *R. vomitoria*) are used in the treatment of malaria in the eastern part of Africa [38].

However, more than 50% of the species used in Bukavu, are used at Butembo. These are: *Allium sativum*, *Catharanthus roseus*, *Ageratum conyzoides*, *Artemisia annua*, *Bidens pilosa*, *Matricaria chamomilla*, *Tithonia diversifolia*, *Vernonia amygdalina*, *Anana cosmesus*, *Chenopodium ambrosioides*, *Carica papaya*, *Cupressus lusitanica*, *Arachis hypogaea*, *Cassia occidentalis*, *Erythrina abyssinica*, *Mentha piperita*, *Persea americana*, *Azadirachta indica*, *Eucalyptus globulus*, *Psidium guayava*, *Passiflora foetida* (Near of *P. edulis*), *Cymbopogon citratus*, *Cinchona ledgeriana*, *Citrus limon*, *Physalis peruviana*, *Lantana camara* and *Aloe ssp.* [21].

Some of these plant species are also reported by some authors as antimalarial recipes in African, American, European and Asian traditional medicine [2,39-61].

Azadirachta indica is the species most frequently mentioned (42.5%), followed by *Cymbopogon citratus* (20.4%).

CONCLUSION

The study lists some plant species used in the treatment of malaria in Butembo, a city located in the east part of the Democratic Republic of the Congo. Literature confirms some plants activities in other African parts. The herbal remedies used against malaria and pharmacological studies of these preparations are necessary and might lead to interesting antimalarial remedies. Apart from well-established plants like cinchona and artemisia, studies need to be done on some promising plants to determine antimalarial/antiplasmodial

activity, isolate bioactive compound(s) and determine their structure(s) and their toxicity.

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